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MODELING THE GENETIC CODE: P -ADIC APPROACH

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The genetic code (GC) plays a central role in all living organisms. From a mathematical point of view, the GC is a map from a set of 64 elements (which are codons) onto a set of 21 elements (which are 20 amino acids and 1 stop signal). The GC is the result of evolution, experimentally deciphered as early as the mid-1960s, but its satisfactory theoretical understanding does not yet exist. There are many papers on the GC modeling, its origin and evolution, but also many unsolved issues. In this contribution we provide a brief overview of genetic code modeling, highlighting the p -adic approach, which can describe many properties of the GC. Our primary mathematical tool is a p -adic distance, which simply and adequately describes similarities within the GC. We also point how one could apply this mathematical method to other sequences with a bioinformatic content.

1. Introduction

Life on our planet emerged when the age of the universe was about 10 billion years, i.e. about 3.8 billion years ago. Many processes must take place in evolution of the universe to create the conditions for emergence of life. All living organisms have some common inherent properties and one of them is the genetic code (GC). The genetic code was formed at the very early beginning of life and its general characteristics have remained almost unchanged during biological evolution. Moreover, there is a general opinion that there was the Last Universal Common Ancestor (LUCA) with the GC almost the same as it is nowadays. Hence, one can say that the GC is one of the invariants of evolution.

The genetic code connects codons in genes and amino acids in proteins, as well as specifies the codons responsible for a stop signal in protein synthesis. From a mathematical point of view, the genetic code is a map from

the set of 64 codons onto the set of 21 elements (which are 20 amino acids and 1 stop signal). The genetic code is a well-known experimental fact that tells us which concrete codons code any of amino acids, and which codons code stop (termination) signal.

The absence of valuable facts from the initial period of the life origin gives rise to different hypotheses about the emergence of the genetic code. The stereochemical and coevolution theory start from assumption that the GC is determined by some physicochemical processes. However, many processes on primitive Earth were very complex and stochastic. Hence, the very beginning of the genetic code formation should be considered in the light of a certain ambiguity, which was gradually by increasing some regularities and became “frozen” [9]. For a review of these approaches to the life origin, the very early evolution and meaning of the genetic code, see papers [1, 2, 3] on code biology. Anyhow, the GC was present already in the LUCA and has evolved to nowadays into about 30 versions, differing only in the few assignments of codons to amino acids (or stop signal).

The genetic code was experimentally deciphered in the mid of 1960s [5]. It is usually presented by an appropriate table that precisely defines the codon relation to an amino acid or stop signal. Thus the structure of the genetic code is well known experimentally. However, there is still a problem with its complete theoretical description and understanding, so there are still numerous questions without satisfactory answers. The biggest question is: “Why is the genetic code the way it is and how did it come to be?” This is especially significant in light of the facts that there are theoretically about 1.5×10^{84} [18] possibilities to connect codons and amino acids, such that any amino acid is coded at least by one codon, while only a few dozens of versions of the GC have been found in living organisms.

Another significant problem is finding a satisfactory theoretical explanation for the existing genetic code *degeneracy*. The degeneracy is due to the fact that there are 64 codons and only 20 proteinogenic amino acids, which results in that most of the amino acids encoded by more than one codon, where there are generally a huge number of possibilities for assigning codons to amino acids. For example, in the vertebrate mitochondrial (VM) code, an amino acid is coded by either two, four or six codons.

It is worth noting that the ultimate goal of any theoretical research is to understand the maximum of experimental facts in terms of the minimum of theoretical concepts and assumptions. The starting point for a theoretical comprehension of the experimental data is the construction of a relevant model. An actual model should be able not only to describe all

known facts about the phenomenon in question but also to be able to make predictions that can be verified experimentally. In this way, a successful model becomes an appropriate theory. In some new theories understanding cannot be achieved within the framework of old concepts, but only within new concepts and new laws. Illustrative examples come from physics. For example, quantum theory in comparison with classical mechanics is based on a concept of quanta, which is new and nonclassical one, and quantum phenomena cannot be comprehended in terms of classical concepts, but should be viewed within the formalism of quantum theory.

There are many, and rather different, approaches to modeling of the genetic code, which usually depend on the scientific background of the researchers involved. So, there are mathematical, physical, chemical, biological and some other approaches. A brief review of some theoretical modelings of the genetic code will be presented in Section 4.

The genetic code model we consider in this article is based on a p -adic distance that serves as a mathematical tool for describing the similarity between codons, the similarity between amino acids, and connection between codons and amino acids. This model was proposed in 2006 [21] and has been further considered and developed, mainly in [11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 18, 19, 20, 35]. The idea behind this approach is as follows. In the genetic code, a codon represents information, while an amino acid (or a stop signal) represents the meaning of this information. Multiple codons that code the same amino acid (or stop signal) have the same meaning and thus should be closest in an informational sense. If so, the question arises: How to describe this closeness (nearness, similarity)? The relevant answer provides a table of the vertebrate mitochondrial code, where it can be observed that two codons which have the same first two nucleotides have the same meaning. This property suggests the assumption that codons should be elements of an ultrametric space with a p -adic distance. In Dragovich's approach, this assumption was the starting point for modeling the genetic code by using 5-adic and 2-adic distances. According to this assumption, it has been shown that two vertebrate mitochondrial codons that are closest under both 5-adic and 2-adic distances code the same amino acid or stop signal. This p -adic model describes the degeneracy of the genetic code very well, as well as some of its other properties. Another similar model of the genetic code was considered on a dyadic plane, see [31].

This is a review paper with some new insights into genetic code modeling, emphasizing the approach with p -adic distance.

Section 2 contains basic facts about the genetic code. In Sect. 3 we present the relevant p -adic mathematical background, in particular related to the p -adic distance. A brief review of various approaches for the genetic code modeling is contained in Sect. 4. Various aspects of p -adic modeling of the standard and vertebrate mitochondrial genetic codes are considered in Sect. 5. In particular, it is shown that the genetic code can be viewed as a translation between the four genetic languages, as well as an ultrametric tree, a fractal and a p -adic network. Some remarks on extension of p -adic approach to study similarity between nucleotide sequences longer than codons are subject of Section 6, which also contains some remarks on measuring similarity.

2. Basic Experimental Facts about the Genetic Code

To make this paper self-contained, here we provide a brief overview of some main facts about gene expression and the genetic code.

2.1. *Biomolecular background of the genetic code expression*

All biomolecular components and processes associated with the genetic code are within living cells. Expression of the genetic information begins with DNA and ends with syntheses of proteins.

Information about the primary structure of proteins and regulation of various processes (including growth and reproduction) is stored in DNA (deoxyribonucleic acid). DNA is a macromolecule composed of two polynucleotide strands that twist around each other to form a double helix. The nucleotide consists of a nucleic acid base, a sugar and a phosphate group. DNA contains four nucleic acid bases: adenine (A), cytosine (C), guanine (G) and thymine (T). Adenine and guanine are purines that are composed of two carbon-nitrogen rings. Cytosine and thymine are pyrimidines, containing one carbon-nitrogen ring. As information, nucleobases and nucleotides have the same meaning. The bases in the strands are connected complementarily, making the base pairs A-T and C-G, i.e. A in one chain corresponds to T in another and also applies to C and G.

In the human DNA, there are about 3×10^9 base pairs and about 20,000 protein-coding genes, which occupy approximately 1.5% of the entire genome. The rest of DNA is a non-protein coding portion that is linked to instructions for regulating gene expression and other cellular processes. There are two important processes with genetic information of DNA: repli-

cation and transcription. Replication duplicates DNA, yielding two DNA molecules with the same genetic content as the original.

Ribonucleic acid (RNA) is a polynucleotide chain. There are many kinds of RNA, in particular microRNA, that play various roles in processes from transcription to protein synthesis. As a result of gene transcription from DNA, primary messenger RNA (pre-mRNA) is obtained, so that the bases A, C, T, G are respectively transcribed to their complements: $C \rightarrow G$, $A \rightarrow U$, $T \rightarrow A$, $G \rightarrow C$, where U denotes uracil (which is a pyrimidine). This pre-mRNA, a transcript from DNA, in the eucariote contains exons and introns. During the splicing process, the introns are removed and a mature mRNA containing only exons is obtained. In the splicing process, exons can be joined in different ways, creating different possibilities, and as a result several proteins can be obtained from a single gene. Mature mRNA contains only codons, that are ordered trinucleotides. There are $4^3 = 64$ codons and any codon codes either an amino acid or a stop signal.

A very important role in the translation of genetic information contained in mRNA play transfer RNA (tRNA) and aminoacyl-tRNA synthetases, which are adaptors between codons and amino acids. A tRNA is 73-93 nucleotides long chain that has cloverleaf form and contains an anticodon. An aminoacyl-tRNA synthetase is a protein that binds the appropriate amino acid to the relevant tRNA. There is only one aminoacyl-tRNA synthetase for each of the 20 amino acids. It is worth pointing out that a tRNA represents the physical link between the anticodon and the amino acid, according to the genetic code table.

Protein synthesis is performed within ribosomes, which are complex macromolecular machines composed of ribosomal RNAs and ribosomal proteins. A ribosome consists of two subunits: the smaller subunit allows the reading of a sequence of codons in the mRNA, while the larger subunit allows the binding of amino acids into the polypeptide chain in the same order as the codons in mRNA. The translation of codons into amino acids is strictly determined by the genetic code.

Proteins [24] are long polypeptides whose primary structure is the amino acids sequence determined by the codon sequence in the mRNA. There are 20 standard (canonical) and 2 nonstandard amino acids from which proteins are made. Some proteins also undergo post-translation modification. As a result of folding, proteins get a three-dimensional structure that virtually determines their function. Performing various functions, proteins are essential constituents of all living organisms.

2.2. Basic properties of the genetic code

In the previous subsection we briefly outlined main biomolecular systems used in the process of translating genetic information, stored in a protein-coding sequence of codons into DNA and realized as 20 standard amino acids. Each codon is translated to a specific single amino acid or stop (terminal) signal.

Table 1. A common table of the standard genetic code. It represents a link between 64 codons in mRNA and 20 amino acids (aa) with a single stop signal. The code degeneracy is as follows: 2 aa are coded by 1 codon, 9 aa by 2 codons, 1 aa and stop signal by 3 codons, 5 aa by 4 codons, and 3 aa by 6 codons.

UUU Phe (F)	UCU Ser (S)	UAU Tyr (Y)	UGU Cys (C)
UUC Phe (F)	UCC Ser (S)	UAC Tyr (Y)	UGC Cys (C)
UUA Leu (L)	UCA Ser (S)	UAA Ter (*)	UGA Ter (*)
UUG Leu (L)	UCG Ser (S)	UAG Ter (*)	UGG Trp (W)
CUU Leu (L)	CCU Pro (P)	CAU His (H)	CGU Arg (R)
CUC Leu (L)	CCC Pro (P)	CAC His (H)	CGC Arg (R)
CUA Leu (L)	CCA Pro (P)	CAA Gln (Q)	CGA Arg (R)
CUG Leu (L)	CCG Pro (P)	CAG Gln (Q)	CGG Arg (R)
AUU Ile (I)	ACU Thr (T)	AAU Asn (N)	AGU Ser (S)
AUC Ile (I)	ACC Thr (T)	AAC Asn (N)	AGC Ser (S)
AUA Ile (I)	ACA Thr (T)	AAA Lys (K)	AGA Arg (R)
AUG Met (M)	ACG Thr (T)	AAG Lys (K)	AGG Arg (R)
GUU Val (V)	GCU Ala (A)	GAU Asp (D)	GGU Gly (G)
GUC Val (V)	GCC Ala (A)	GAC Asp (D)	GGC Gly (G)
GUA Val (V)	GCA Ala (A)	GAA Glu (E)	GGA Gly (G)
GUG Val (V)	GCG Ala (A)	GAG Glu (E)	GGG Gly (G)

There are about 30 detected variants of the genetic coding, which differ slightly with respect to the meaning of several codons. The standard genetic code, presented in Table 1, is almost universal. It was the first known and deciphered in the mid-1960th. The second code was discovered in human mitochondrial genes in 1979, and is also present in mitochondria of other vertebrates.

All genetic codes have many characteristics in common, e.g. the same 64 codons and 20 amino acids. The nucleotide sequence is read in the 5' to 3' direction. In addition to stop codons, there is also initial codon, that stands at the beginning of mRNA and is usually AUG with meaning of methionine.

The vertebrate mitochondrial code is simpler than the standard one and is presented in Table 2. All other versions of the genetic code, including

the standard one, can theoretically be seen as minor modifications of the VM code. For instance, the standard genetic code generates from the VM code by the following transformations:

- AUA : Met \rightarrow Ile,
- AGA and AGG : Ter \rightarrow Arg,
- UGA : Trp \rightarrow Ter.

Table 2. The vertebrate mitochondrial code. It can be said that the amino acids and stop signal are coded by doublets. Specifically, there are: 2 amino acids (Ser, Leu) coded by 3 doublets; 6 aa (Pro, Thr, Ala, Val, Arg, Gly) coded by 2 doublets; 12 aa (His, Gln, Asn, Lys, Tyr, Asp, Glu, Ile, Met, Phe, Cys, Trp) coded by single doublets; and stop signal (Ter) coded by 2 doublets.

UUU Phe (F)	UCU Ser (S)	UAU Tyr (Y)	UGU Cys (C)
UUC Phe (F)	UCC Ser (S)	UAC Tyr (Y)	UGC Cys (C)
UUA Leu (L)	UCA Ser (S)	UAA Ter (*)	UGA Trp (W)
UUG Leu (L)	UCG Ser (S)	UAG Ter (*)	UGG Trp (W)
CUU Leu (L)	CCU Pro (P)	CAU His (H)	CGU Arg (R)
CUC Leu (L)	CCC Pro (P)	CAC His (H)	CGC Arg (R)
CUA Leu (L)	CCA Pro (P)	CAA Gln (Q)	CGA Arg (R)
CUG Leu (L)	CCG Pro (P)	CAG Gln (Q)	CGG Arg (R)
AUU Ile (I)	ACU Thr (T)	AAU Asn (N)	AGU Ser (S)
AUC Ile (I)	ACC Thr (T)	AAC Asn (N)	AGC Ser (S)
AUA Met (I)	ACA Thr (T)	AAA Lys (K)	AGA Ter (*)
AUG Met (M)	ACG Thr (T)	AAG Lys (K)	AGG Ter (*)
GUU Val (V)	GCU Ala (A)	GAU Asp (D)	GGU Gly (G)
GUC Val (V)	GCC Ala (A)	GAC Asp (D)	GGC Gly (G)
GUA Val (V)	GCA Ala (A)	GAA Glu (E)	GGA Gly (G)
GUG Val (V)	GCG Ala (A)	GAG Glu (E)	GGG Gly (G)

3. p -Adic Mathematical Background

Since we use a p -adic approach to model the genetic code, it is useful to provide the necessary mathematical background. We would like to present p -adic distance and some other mathematical concepts in a way to be comprehensible to a wide audience interested in modeling of the genetic code.

As the usual distance is an adequate mathematical tool to describe position in our ordinary space, so p -adic distance can be used to measure positions in a bioinformation space. In particular, p -adic distance is an adequate mathematical tool for describing the closeness (nearness) of codons

in the genetic coding. For example, codons that are at the smallest p -adic distance code the same or similar amino acid.

In the word “ p -adic”, p denotes a prime number. Recall that a prime number is a natural number greater than 1 that is divisible only by itself and 1. There are infinitely many prime numbers: 2, 3, 5, 7, 11, ... Any natural number greater than 1, is either a prime or composite number, which is a unique product of primes. For example, $4 = 2 \cdot 2$, $6 = 2 \cdot 3$. Prime numbers play a significant role in number theory, p -adic analysis and many other parts of mathematics. In this paper, we are mainly interested in p -adic distance and its application in the genetic code modeling.

It is natural to start with the p -adic norm (also named the p -adic absolute value), which can be defined as follows. Any integer number $m \neq 0$, with respect to a given prime p , can be represented as $m = p^k a$, where $k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$ and a is another integer not divisible by p . By definition, the p -adic norm of $m = p^k a \neq 0$ (denoted by $|m|_p$) is $|m|_p = p^{-k}$. If $m = 0$, then by definition $|0|_p = 0$. One can easily conclude that $|m|_p = p^{-k} \leq 1$, where m is any integer and p is any prime number. It is worth illustrating the p -adic norm by the following example:

$$|500|_p = |2^2 \times 5^3|_p = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{4} & \text{if } p = 2, \\ 1 & \text{if } p = 3, \\ \frac{1}{125} & \text{if } p = 5, \\ 1 & \text{if } p \geq 7. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

p -Adic distance between any two integers x and y is defined as

$$d_p(x, y) = |x - y|_p. \quad (2)$$

For example, let $x = 80$ and $y = 5$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} d_p(80, 5) &= |80 - 5|_p = |75|_p = |3 \times 5^2|_p \\ &= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } p = 2, \\ \frac{1}{3} & \text{if } p = 3, \\ \frac{1}{25} & \text{if } p = 5, \\ 1 & \text{if } p \geq 7. \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

It can easily be concluded that: a) for fixed numbers x and y , p -adic distance depends on p , b) for infinitely many primes p , distance is the same and equal to 1, c) p -adic distance has discrete values, d) inequality $d_p(x, y) \leq 1$ holds for any integers x and y and any prime p .

The p -adic norm and distance are similar in form and very different in properties from the well-known usual absolute value (denoted by $|x|$), and the related distance is $d(x, y) = |x - y|$. Recall that absolute value of number x is

$$|x| = \begin{cases} x & \text{if } x \text{ is positive,} \\ -x & \text{if } x \text{ is negative,} \\ 0 & \text{if } x = 0. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

However, there is an interesting connection between p -adic norms and absolute value in the form of their product, i.e.

$$|x| \prod_p |x|_p = 1, \quad (5)$$

where x is any integer different from 0. Formula (5) follows from the fact that any non-zero integer x can be presented as the product $x = \pm p_1^{k_1} p_2^{k_2} \dots p_n^{k_n}$, where p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n is a finite set of some prime numbers, and k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n are some natural numbers. Then $\prod_p |x|_p = p_1^{-k_1} p_2^{-k_2} \dots p_n^{-k_n}$, while ordinary absolute value $|x| = p_1^{k_1} p_2^{k_2} \dots p_n^{k_n}$. It is not difficult to conclude that product formula (5) also holds for any non-zero rational number.

Formula

$$|x| \prod_p |x|_p = 1, x \in \mathbb{Q} \quad (6)$$

is a simple example of adelic products and is related to adeles. An adèle x is an infinite sequence [28]

$$x = (x_\infty, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_p, \dots), \quad (7)$$

where x_∞ is a real number and x_p is a p -adic number with the restriction that for all but a finite set of primes p has to be satisfied $|x|_p \leq 1$. A special case, called principal adèle, is when the same integer or rational number is treated as real and as p -adic for all primes. The adelic approach gives the possibility to treat integers, as well as rational numbers, simultaneously with respect to all nontrivial norms and achieving important results like formula (6). Application of adeles should give a more complete description of the genetic code.

p -Adic distance is the most significant and exploited example of ultrametrics. The ultrametric space is a set U endowed with a distance d with

the following properties:

$$\begin{aligned}
 (i) \quad & d(x, y) \geq 0, \quad d(x, y) = 0 \text{ if and only if } x = y, \\
 (ii) \quad & d(x, y) = d(y, x), \\
 (iii) \quad & d(x, y) \leq \max\{d(x, z), d(z, y)\},
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

where $x, y, z \in U$. Property (iii) is commonly referred to as the strong triangle inequality, but it is also known as ultrametric or non-Archimedean inequality. The p -adic distance defined in (2) satisfies all properties in (8). On some applications of ultrametrics in physics and biology, we refer to the review [37]. Ultrametrics is an adequate mathematical tool for the description of the nested structure in hierarchical systems.

According to the properties of p -adic distance, it follows that two integers are closer when their difference is more divisible by prime number p . It can also be well illustrated presenting numbers by expansion in base p , i.e.

$$\begin{aligned}
 x &= x_0 + x_1p + x_2p^2 + \dots + x_kp^k \equiv x_0 x_1 x_2 \dots x_k, \\
 y &= y_0 + y_1p + y_2p^2 + \dots + y_kp^k \equiv y_0 y_1 y_2 \dots y_k,
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

where $x_i \in \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$ and $y_i \in \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$ are related digits. Then, p -adic distance between x and y from (9) is

$$\begin{aligned}
 d_p(x, y) &= |x - y|_p \\
 &= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x_0 \neq y_0, \\ \frac{1}{p} & \text{if } x_0 = y_0, x_1 \neq y_1, \\ \frac{1}{p^2} & \text{if } x_0 = y_0, x_1 = y_1, x_2 \neq y_2, \\ \dots & \dots \dots \dots, \\ \frac{1}{p^k} & \text{if } x_0 = y_0, \dots, x_{k-1} = y_{k-1}, x_k \neq y_k. \end{cases}
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

From (10), we see how the p -adic distance depends on the digits. If the first digits are different, then the distance is maximal and does not depend on the values of the others. Two integers are closer when they have more equal digits counting from the beginning.

As integers endowed by ordinary absolute value are real integers, so integers endowed by p -adic norm are p -adic integers. It is useful to distinguish real and p -adic integers representing their digits in the opposite direction, for example:

$$\begin{aligned}
 x &= x_kp^k + \dots + x_1p + x_0 \equiv x_k \dots x_1 x_0 \quad (\text{real}), \\
 x &= x_0 + x_1p + \dots + x_kp^k \equiv x_0 x_1 \dots x_k \quad (p\text{-adic}).
 \end{aligned}$$

Note that in the real case the term $x_k p^k$ is the largest, while in the p -adic case is the smallest, and vice versa for term x_0 . Therefore, what is “large” or “small” depends on the applied norm (ordinary or p -adic absolute value).

p -Adic analogs of the field of real numbers \mathbb{R} are the fields of p -adic numbers \mathbb{Q}_p , a separate field for each p . p -Adic numbers were invented by Kurt Hensel in 1897. There is p -adic analysis [38, 41], which has applications in modeling systems with a hierarchical structure and is known as *p-adic mathematical physics*, for some reviews see [6, 16, 17, 47]. In p -adic modeling of the genetic code, it is generally sufficient to use the relevant p -adic distance between integers.

4. Modeling of the Genetic Code

Before we begin with p -adic modeling of the genetic code, we will present a brief review of some other approaches. We will follow mostly the chronological appearance of new proposals. An overview of the topic could also be given in accordance with different scientific perspectives, which may be mathematical, physical, chemical, biological, informational and multidisciplinary.

The first theoretical assumptions about the genetic code began shortly after the discovery of the helicoidal structure of DNA by J. Watson and F. Crick in 1953 [48]. The first model was constructed by the physicist G. Gamow and is known as the *diamond code* [27]. After that, it is worth mentioning Crick’s *comma-free code* in 1957 [7]. Although these two models were very well conceived, they are wrong because the biological aspects were not taken into account (for a review of this first phase of the modeling, see [29]). Nevertheless, Gamow’s idea that genetic information should be coded by ordered triplets of nucleotides was correct and well confirmed. Many papers on GC have been published since that time and studies are also actual nowadays.

Note that the genetic code was experimentally deciphered in the mid-1960s, which made its modeling possible on a much more realistic basis than before. Specifically, the assignment of the codons to the amino acids was started by M. W. Nirenberg and J. H. Matthaei in 1961 and mostly completed in 1965 [5]. In the sequel of this section, we will mention several models to illustrate a variety of approaches.

In 1966 [39] and 1968 [40], Yu. B. Rumer noted that there are 32 codons contained in 8 quadruplets for which nucleotide at the third position is irrelevant for coding. Accordingly, Rumer introduced notions of 8 strong

(CC, AC, UC, GC, CU, GU, CG, GG) and 8 weak (CA, AA, UA, GA, AU, UU, AG, UG) roots of codons, and classified nucleotides: C – very strong, G – strong, U = T – weak, and A – very weak. He introduced symmetric transformations between bases and between codons, see also a brief review [22].

To explain the degeneracy of the genetic code, Crick in 1966 [8] proposed the wobble hypothesis for a codon-anticodon pairing at the third base of codons in mRNA. This feature will be considered in more details in the sequel of this article. In 1968 Crick [9] also considered the origin of genetic code and concluded that it was frozen after some initial developments.

In a series of papers started in 1965 [49], C. R. Woese investigated the origins and evolution of genetic code, in particular the mechanisms of codon-amino acid assignment.

R. Swanson investigated the GC as a type of Gray Code, where amino acids are divided into four groups (small, large, external, internal), [46].

In the 1990s, several authors considered algebraic approach, in fact some Lie groups and algebraic structures, to model the structure of genetic code. This research was influenced by the use of similar methods in high energy physics. In the paper from 1993 [30], J.E.M. Hornos and Y.M.M. Hornos considered a 64-dimensional irreducible representation of the symplectic $Sp(6)$ group as well as irreducible representations of the subalgebras and obtained an approximative model of the GC degeneracy. Similar supersymmetric models of the GC can be seen in [4] and [25]. Another approach based on a quantum algebra has been explored, see [26] and references therein.

In V.I. Shcherbak papers [42, 43, 44, 45], the various arithmetic regularities inside the GC determined by the masses of its constituents (the amino acids and nucleobases), primarily for the code degeneracy pattern in the form of the aforementioned Rumer's division are presented. Further analysis of the mass distribution confirmed the mass balances at the protein level [10]. These studies have motivated further similar research [36] and deepened the "enigma" of the GC origin related to the underlying selective mechanisms involved in its shaping [34, 35].

p -Adic modeling of the genetic code was proposed in 2006 [21] and further developed mainly in [14, 15, 18, 20].

A recent review on the noise immunity, frameshift problem, circular codes and some symmetries, can be seen in [23].

The origin and early evolution of life and genetic code are inevitably correlated. About this subject, one can see recent reviews [2, 32, 33] and

references therein. The origin and early evolution of genetic code were also conjectured within p -adic modeling [14], according to which there were three steps in the codon formation (single nucleotides \rightarrow dinucleotides \rightarrow trinucleotides).

5. p -Adic Modeling of the Genetic Code

5.1. Genetic code as the language of life

It is useful to present genetic coding as a translation between the four sub-languages of the universal language of life, as reported in our recent paper [20]. We will use this point of view in the p -adic modeling of GC.

To this end, let us first recall some relevant notions from the theory of formal languages. An *alphabet* is a finite set of elements which are called *letters*, which can be denoted as $\mathcal{A} = \{a, b, c, \dots\}$. A *word* over this alphabet \mathcal{A} is any finite string (sequence) of letters. Thus, the words of length n are elements of $\mathcal{A}^n = \{x_1x_2 \dots x_n : x_i \in \mathcal{A}\}$. The language \mathcal{L} over alphabet \mathcal{A} is a subset of the set of all possible words that can be constructed over alphabet \mathcal{A} .

We find it useful to introduce four kinds of biomolecular languages with related alphabets. These four alphabets are

$$\mathcal{A}_1 = \{A, C, G, T\}, \quad (11)$$

$$\mathcal{A}_2 = \{A, C, G, U\}, \quad (12)$$

$$\mathcal{A}_3 = \{A, C, G, U, I\}, \quad (13)$$

$$\mathcal{A}_4 = \{M_1, M_2, \dots, M_{20}\}, \quad (14)$$

and they generate the corresponding four languages:

$$\mathcal{L}_1 = \{N_1N_2N_3 : N_i \in \mathcal{A}_1\}, \quad (15)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_2 = \{N_1N_2N_3 : N_i \in \mathcal{A}_2\}, \quad (16)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_3 \subset \{N_1N_2N_3 : N_i \in \mathcal{A}_3\}, \quad (17)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_4 = \{\text{a set of proteins}\}, \quad (18)$$

where A, C, G, T, U are standard nucleotides, I is inosine, and M_1, M_2, \dots, M_{20} are twenty canonical amino acids. Recall that inosine is a nucleoside whose counterpart base is hypoxanthine, which is a purine. Thus, the alphabets $\mathcal{A}_1, \mathcal{A}_2, \mathcal{A}_3$ altogether contain three pyrimidines (C, T, U) and three purines (A, G, I). Inosine is a constituent of some anticodons in tRNAs and plays an important role in the wobble base pairing.

The languages \mathcal{L}_1 , \mathcal{L}_2 , and \mathcal{L}_3 have three-letter words called codons (anticodons). \mathcal{L}_1 and \mathcal{L}_2 contain 64 words (codons), and are all employed by the genetic code. \mathcal{L}_3 contains 125 words, however only some of them are embodied in tRNA according to the wobble pairing.

The first step: translation from $\mathcal{L}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{L}_2$. This is the transcription of a gene from DNA with subsequent splicing to the mature mRNA. In this process, the codons in a gene are translated into their anticodons according to the Watson-Crick complementary base pairing, i.e.

$$C \rightarrow G; \quad G \rightarrow C; \quad T \rightarrow A; \quad A \rightarrow U. \quad (19)$$

The second step: translation from $\mathcal{L}_2 \rightarrow \mathcal{L}_3$. This is the translation from language \mathcal{L}_2 to language \mathcal{L}_3 . In this case, translation of letters from $\mathcal{A}_2 \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_3$ depends on the letter position in words according to the next two rules.

(i) At the first two positions of nucleotides in codons, translation is ruled by Watson-Crick base pairing

$$C \rightarrow G; \quad G \rightarrow C; \quad U \rightarrow A; \quad A \rightarrow U. \quad (20)$$

(ii) At the third position of codons translation is according to Crick's wobble hypothesis:

$$\begin{array}{ll} C \rightarrow G, I; & A \rightarrow U, I; \\ U \rightarrow A, G, I; & G \rightarrow C, U. \end{array} \quad (21)$$

It can be easily seen from (21) that the translation at the third position is not one-to-one as in (20), but there is some ambiguity. This ambiguity enables some anticodons in tRNA to recognize more than one codon in mRNA according to wobbling over the third position of codons:

$$\begin{array}{ll} C \rightsquigarrow G; & A \rightsquigarrow U; \\ U \rightsquigarrow A, G; & G \rightsquigarrow C, U; \quad I \rightsquigarrow C, A, U. \end{array} \quad (22)$$

It follows from (22) that wobble is related to U, G , and particularly to I .

Note that the first two nucleotides of codons in DNA are equal to the corresponding two nucleotides of anticodons in tRNA. Hence, the genetic code is a mapping from the codons in DNA to the amino acids.

The third step: translation from $\mathcal{L}_3 \rightarrow \mathcal{L}_4$. This is the translation from an anticodon in tRNA to the corresponding amino acid attached to the same tRNA. Note that \mathcal{L}_3 has $5 \times 5 \times 5 = 125$ words, but only a part is employed in translation to \mathcal{L}_4 . This part of 125 is related to the number of tRNAs that can unambiguously translate anticodons into amino acids – in

the case of the standard genetic code 31 is the minimal and 41 the maximal number of tRNAs. This is an example of the economic functioning of living cells. This third step is the translation of some words from \mathcal{L}_3 to 20 letters of \mathcal{L}_4 .

5.2. Codons in the form of an ultrametric tree

In Subsection 5.1, we introduced four languages that are used sequentially to translate genetic information from DNA to the protein synthesis. The genetic code is usually considered as a translation of codons from mRNA to amino acids in proteins, i.e. translation of language \mathcal{L}_2 to language \mathcal{L}_4 . The language \mathcal{L}_2 of 64 codons can be represented as an ultrametric space.

One of the characteristics of GC is that the first two nucleotides in codons play a more important role than the third one. Almost always, when two codons have the same first two nucleotides and the third is pyrimidine, then they code the same amino acid or stop signal. A similar situation is when purine is in the third place. This fact leads to the conclusion that 64 codons are ordered according to ultrametric distance.

Example 1. The following example of an ultrametric distance is suitable to represent a codon space as an ultrametric tree. For this purpose, let the distance between any two words x and y be $d_u(x, y) = (n - k)/n$, where n is the number of letters in the words, and k is the number of letters equal in both words counting positions from the beginning. This distance has discrete values between 0 and 1 as follows:

$$d_u(x, y) = \frac{n - k}{n} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } k = 0, \\ 1 - \frac{1}{n}, & \text{if } k = 1, \\ \dots & \dots \\ 0, & \text{if } k = n. \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

Note that a smaller k implies a larger distance and vice versa.

One can easily conclude that distance (23) satisfies the properties (i) and (ii) of ultrametrics (8). Property (iii) (i.e. strong triangle inequality) can be proved in the following way. Let distances between three words x, y and z (of the same length n) are: $d_u(x, y) = (n - k)/n$, $d_u(x, z) = (n - k_1)/n$, $d_u(y, z) = (n - k_2)/n$. The difference between these distances depends on numbers k, k_1, k_2 . It is important to observe that two of these numbers k, k_1, k_2 are always equal and the third one is greater or equal to the other two. Without loss of generality, let $k \geq k_1 = k_2$. Then there are

the following two possibilities:

$$d_u(x, y) = d_u(x, z) = d_u(y, z) \quad \text{if } k = k_1 = k_2, \quad (24)$$

$$d_u(x, y) < d_u(x, z) = d_u(y, z) \quad \text{if } k > k_1 = k_2. \quad (25)$$

Properties (24) and (26) can be rewritten in the form $d_u(x, y) \leq \max\{d_u(x, z), d_u(y, z)\}$, what is just property (iii) in (8).

To apply above introduced ultrametrics of words to codons, note that in this case $n = 3$ and $m \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ for mutually different words. Let codons x, y and z be $x = x_0x_1x_2, y = y_0y_1y_2$ and $z = z_0z_1z_2$, where the letters are from the alphabet \mathcal{A}_1 or \mathcal{A}_2 . Then,

$$d_u(x, y) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x_0 \neq y_0, \\ \frac{2}{3}, & \text{if } x_0 = y_0, x_1 \neq y_1, \\ \frac{1}{3}, & \text{if } x_0 = y_0, x_1 = y_1, x_2 \neq y_2. \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

The corresponding strong triangle inequality can be illustrated by the following two examples:

(i) If $x_0 = y_0$ and $x_0 \neq z_0$ then

$$d_u(x, y) < d_u(x, z) = d_u(y, z). \quad (27)$$

(ii) If $x_0 = y_0, x_1 = y_1$ and $x_0 \neq z_0$ then

$$d_u(x, y) < d_u(x, z) = d_u(y, z). \quad (28)$$

The ultrametricity of the codon space is illustrated by the related ultrametric tree in Fig. 1.

Example 2. Another example of ultrametrics is the Baire distance, which is defined for infinitely long sequences. For example,

$$d_B(x, y) = 2^{-k} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } k = 0, \\ \frac{1}{2}, & \text{if } k = 1, \\ \frac{1}{4}, & \text{if } k = 2, \\ \dots\dots\dots & \\ 0, & \text{if } k = \infty, \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

where k is the same as in the previous example, i.e. the longest common prefix of sequences x and y . Instead of base 2, any other natural number greater than 2 may also be used. However, the Baire distance is not quite appropriate for codons, since codons are three-letter sequences.

Example 3. The p -adic distance, presented in Section 3, is the most significant example of ultrametrics and the most suitable for investigating

numbers in such a way that the digits in those numbers correspond to the nucleotides in the codons. To this end, we must consider that the nucleobases that are purines, as well as those that are pyrimidines, are closer than a purine and a pyrimidine.

Note that three pyrimidines (C, T, U) and three purines (A, G, I), where I stands for inosine, participate in GC. Since T (thymine) and U (uracil) are virtually equivalent, there are five nucleotides remaining that we should associate with five relevant digits. This suggests taking prime number five ($p = 5$) as the base and 0, 1, 2, 3, 4 as the corresponding digits. Then 64 three-digit numbers can be constructed using 1, 2, 3, 4 and also some similar numbers by adding the digit 0 at the first place.

The question now is how to connect nucleotides and digits in detail. In previous papers, it was shown that identification $C \equiv 1$, $A \equiv 2$, $T = U \equiv 3$, $G \equiv 4$ works quite well. In our recent paper [20], we added inosine with $I \equiv 0$ and found it suitable. Hence, we take the following identification:

$$I \equiv 0, C \equiv 1, A \equiv 2, U = T \equiv 3, G \equiv 4. \quad (30)$$

Now, instead of the letters $I, C, A, U(T), G$, we will use respectively digits 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, so that alphabets (11) - (13), and the corresponding languages, take the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}_1 &= \{1, 2, 3, 4\} = \mathcal{A}_2, \\ \mathcal{L}_1 = \mathcal{L}_2 &= \{n_0 n_1 n_2 : n_i \in \mathcal{A}_1 = \mathcal{A}_2\}, \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}_3 &= \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}, \\ \mathcal{L}_3 &\subset \{n_0 n_1 n_2 : n_i \in \mathcal{A}_3\}, \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

where in general case

$$n_0 n_1 n_2 \equiv n_0 + n_1 5 + n_2 5^2, \quad n_i \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}, \quad (33)$$

is a set of 125 possible words. The digit 0 representing inosine appears as $n_0 = 0$ only in the anticodons of some tRNAs. When $n_i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ in $n_0 n_1 n_2$, one has 64 standard codons.

According to (10), 5-adic distance between any two different codons, $x = x_0 x_1 x_2$ and $y = y_0 y_1 y_2$, has one of the following three values:

$$\begin{aligned} d_5(x, y) &= |(x_0 + x_1 5 + x_2 5^2) - (y_0 + y_1 5 + y_2 5^2)|_5 \\ &= \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x_0 \neq y_0, \\ \frac{1}{5}, & \text{if } x_0 = y_0, x_1 \neq y_1, \\ \frac{1}{25}, & \text{if } x_0 = y_0, x_1 = y_1, x_2 \neq y_2. \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

Thus, the smallest 5-adic distance, which is $\frac{1}{25}$, arranges 64 codons in mRNA into 16 quadruplets. Within these quadruplets, the first two nucleotides are the same, while at the third position there are two pyrimidines (C, U) and two purines (A, G).

Using a 2-adic distance within quadruplets gives

$$\begin{aligned} d_2(x, y) &= |(n_0 + n_1 5 + x_2 5^2) - (n_0 + n_1 5 + y_2 5^2)|_2 \\ &= |(x_2 - y_2) 25|_2 = |x_2 - y_2|_2 \\ &= \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x_2 - y_2 \neq \pm 2 \\ \frac{1}{2}, & \text{if } x_2 - y_2 = \pm 2. \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

There are two possibilities for $x_2 - y_2 = 2$: 1) $x_2 = U = 3$, $y_2 = C = 1$ and 2) $x_2 = G = 4$, $y_2 = A = 2$. Hence, the smallest 2-adic distance between codons within a quadruplet, which is $\frac{1}{2}$, gives two doublets: one doublet has pyrimidine at the third position, while the other one has purine.

5.4. *Vertebrate mitochondrial and standard code:*

(5, 2)-adic model

Recall that only a few dozen genetic codes are known in living organisms, despite the huge number of possibilities for linking 64 codons and 20 amino acids. Human cells have two codes: the vertebrate mitochondrial code and the standard genetic code. The mitochondrial code is in mitochondria, which is the organelle responsible for generating energy. The vertebrate mitochondrial (VM) code has one of the simplest code symmetries. Its 64 codons can be viewed as 16 quadruplets, within which the 5-adic distance between codons is the smallest, i.e. $d_5(x, y) = \frac{1}{25}$. Each quadruplet consists of two doublets, so that the 2-adic distance between the corresponding codons is $d_2(x, y) = \frac{1}{2}$. Therefore, by successively applying the 5-adic and 2-adic distances, 64 codons form 32 doublets that code 20 amino acids and a stop signal. Namely, 2 amino acids are coded by three doublets, 6 amino acids and stop signal are coded by two doublets, and 12 amino acids are coded by single doublets (see Table 3). In this way, the smallest simultaneous 5-adic and 2-adic distance determines doublets of codons that have the same genetic meaning.

When three doublets code the same amino acid (i.e. leucine or serine), then two doublets are in the same quadruplet, while the third one belongs to the other quadruplet. In the case of leucine, the third doublet should be compared with the second doublet in quadruplet, resulting in a difference only in the first digits. In one doublet the first digit equals 1, while in the

second is 3. It follows that the 2-adic distance between related codons is $d_2(132, 332) = d_2(134, 334) = \frac{1}{2}$, meaning that the 2-adic closeness is the same as between the doublets inside the quadruplets. Situation with serine is similar, i.e. $d_2(241, 311) = d_2(243, 313) = \frac{1}{2}$. There is an easy way to determine the divisibility of an integer number by 2 in 5-adic expansion. Namely, if the sum of digits is even or odd, then the corresponding number is even or odd, respectively.

Table 3. The vertebrate mitochondrial code in 5-adic representation. Nucleotides are related to the digits as follows: C = 1, A = 2, U = 3, G = 4. The 5-adic distance between codons is: $\frac{1}{25}$ within quadruplets, $\frac{1}{5}$ between different quadruplets in the same column, 1 otherwise. Under the 2-adic distance, each quadruplet can be viewed as two doublets, with each doublet coding either an amino acid or termination signal (Ter). The 2-adic distance between codons in doublets is $\frac{1}{2}$. When an amino acid is coded by two doublets then they belong to the same quadruplet. The amino acids leucine (Leu) and serine (Ser) are coded by three doublets – the third doublet is at $\frac{1}{2}$ of the 2-adic distance with respect to the corresponding doublet in quadruplet. It is worth noting that there is symmetry regarding the coding by quadruplets as well as by doublets along the middle vertical line, i.e. there is invariance in quadruplets and doublets under interchange of digits $1 \leftrightarrow 4$ and $2 \leftrightarrow 3$ at the first position. Moreover, doublets form a figure that looks like the letter T.

111	CCC	Pro	211	ACC	Thr	311	UCC	Ser	411	GCC	Ala
112	CCA	Pro	212	ACA	Thr	312	UCA	Ser	412	GCA	Ala
113	CCU	Pro	213	ACU	Thr	313	UCU	Ser	413	GCU	Ala
114	CCG	Pro	214	ACG	Thr	314	UCG	Ser	414	GCG	Ala
121	CAC	His	221	AAC	Asn	321	UAC	Tyr	421	GAC	Asp
122	CAA	Gln	222	AAA	Lys	322	UAA	Ter	422	GAA	Glu
123	CAU	His	223	AAU	Asn	323	UAU	Tyr	423	GAU	Asp
124	CAG	Gln	224	AAG	Lys	324	UAG	Ter	424	GAG	Glu
131	CUC	Leu	231	AUC	Ile	331	UUC	Phe	431	GUC	Val
132	CUA	Leu	232	AUA	Met	332	UUA	Leu	432	GUA	Val
133	CUU	Leu	233	AUU	Ile	333	UUU	Phe	433	GUU	Val
134	CUG	Leu	234	AUG	Met	334	UUG	Leu	434	GUG	Val
141	CGC	Arg	241	AGC	Ser	341	UGC	Cys	441	GGC	Gly
142	CGA	Arg	242	AGA	Ter	342	UGA	Trp	442	GGA	Gly
143	CGU	Arg	243	AGU	Ser	343	UGU	Cys	443	GGU	Gly
144	CGG	Arg	244	AGG	Ter	344	UGG	Trp	444	GGG	Gly

The standard genetic code exists in almost all species living on our planet. It slightly differs from the VM code since only a few codons code different amino acids. The following formal changes in the VM code lead to the standard one: AUA (232): Met \rightarrow Ile; AGA (242) and AGG (244): Ter \rightarrow Arg; UGA (342): Trp \rightarrow Ter. This can be realized by a relevant change in tRNA. For example,

- codon AUA (232) in mRNA, which pairs with anticodon UAU (323) in tRNA of the VM code, pairs with anticodon UAI (320) in the standard code;
- codon AUG (234) in mRNA, which pairs with anticodon UAU (323) in tRNA of the VM code, pairs with anticodon UAC (321) in the standard code.

As a result of these differences, the standard genetic code contains isoleucine (Ile) coded by three codons, as well as methionine (Met) and tryptophan (Trp) coded by single codons, see Table 4. From a simplicity standpoint, the VM code is simpler than the standard one, but the standard code is more advanced than the VM one.

Table 4. The standard genetic code is similar to the VM code – the four codons (232, 242, 244, 342) have a different meaning. It is less symmetrical than the VM code.

111	CCC	Pro	211	ACC	Thr	311	UCC	Ser	411	GCC	Ala
112	CCA	Pro	212	ACA	Thr	312	UCA	Ser	412	GCA	Ala
113	CCU	Pro	213	ACU	Thr	313	UCU	Ser	413	GCU	Ala
114	CCG	Pro	214	ACG	Thr	314	UCG	Ser	414	GCG	Ala
121	CAC	His	221	AAC	Asn	321	UAC	Tyr	421	GAC	Asp
122	CAA	Gln	222	AAA	Lys	322	UAA	Ter	422	GAA	Glu
123	CAU	His	223	AAU	Asn	323	UAU	Tyr	423	GAU	Asp
124	CAG	Gln	224	AAG	Lys	324	UAG	Ter	424	GAG	Glu
131	CUC	Leu	231	AUC	Ile	331	UUC	Phe	431	GUC	Val
132	CUA	Leu	232	AUA	Ile	332	UUA	Leu	432	GUA	Val
133	CUU	Leu	233	AUU	Ile	333	UUU	Phe	433	GUU	Val
134	CUG	Leu	234	AUG	Met	334	UUG	Leu	434	GUG	Val
141	CGC	Arg	241	AGC	Ser	341	UGC	Cys	441	GGC	Gly
142	CGA	Arg	242	AGA	Arg	342	UGA	Ter	442	GGA	Gly
143	CGU	Arg	243	AGU	Ser	343	UGU	Cys	443	GGU	Gly
144	CGG	Arg	244	AGG	Arg	344	UGG	Trp	444	GGG	Gly

Further comparing the standard and VM code, we note that the rule still applies: if two codons code the same amino acid, then they are closest for both 5-adic and 2-adic distance, or at least for one of them. This rule can be generalized to all possible variations of the genetic code as follows: two codons that code the same amino acid or stop signal are p -adic close to at least one p .

5.5. Other p -adic aspects of genetic coding

In the previous part of this section, we have mainly demonstrated the p -adic structure of a set of 64 codons. We want now to briefly present some other properties of the genetic code.

5.5.1. p -Adic properties of amino acids

To apply the above p -adic model for the codons to an amino acid clustering (grouping), it is useful to remind that:

- amino acids coded by codons with the same nucleotide in the second (middle) position have similar physicochemical properties;
- amino acids are physically linked to anticodons within tRNA.

Therefore, it is worth noting that the pairing of the mRNA codon and the corresponding tRNA anticodon is in the following way:

- a nucleotide at the first codon position pairs with its complementary nucleotide at the third anticodon position;
- a nucleotide at the middle codon position pairs with its complementary nucleotide also at the middle anticodon position;
- a nucleotide at the last codon position pairs with its wobble complementary nucleotide at the first anticodon position.

It follows that the middle position is invariant to the codon-anticodon transformation, i.e. the only change in this position is the transition from a given nucleotide to a complementary nucleotide.

To assign a relevant p -adic number to an amino acid, one should look at what are the possible anticodons for a given amino acid. For example, according to the wobble hypothesis, the amino acid glycine (Gly) may be connected by tRNA with the anticodon $XCC = x11$, where $X = I, C, A, U, G$ and $x = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4$. Or, in the case of tyrosine (Tyr), the corresponding anticodon can be $XUA = x32$, where $X = G, A$ and $x = 4, 2$. Since the first position can take different values, while the second and the third are fixed, it seems natural that when assigning a p -adic number to a coding amino acid, the first digit of a total of three digits of related anticodons should be excluded. In the case when six codons code the same amino acid, preference is given to the coding quadruplet. The result of this approach is presented in Table 5.

Some physicochemical similarities of the amino acids in Table 5 are presented below.

Table 5. Here are presented amino acids with the corresponding two-digit 5-adic numbers obtained from related tRNA anticodons. The digit that is related to the middle anticodon position is now at the first position of an amino acid 5-adic number. Amino acids with and without star * belong to the same quadruplet. Tryptophan (Trp) is attributed to the non-occupied number 13 instead of 12, which was attributed to cysteine (Cis) by the above rule. The 5-adic distance between two amino acids in the same row is at least $\frac{1}{5}$, while between amino acids in different rows is equal to 1. Now amino acids in the same row have some similar physicochemical properties.

11 Gly	12 Cys	13 Trp	14 Arg			
21 Val	22 Phe	23 Ile	24 Leu	23* Met		
31 Asp	32 Tyr	33 Asn	34 His	31* Glu	33* Lys	34* Gln
41 Ala	42 Ser	43 Thr	44 Pro			

- First row (digit 1 at the first position): a special case of diversity.
- Second row (digit 2 at the first position): average size and hydrophobic.
- Third row (digit 3 at the first position): average size and hydrophilic.
- Fourth row (digit 4 at the first position): small size and moderate in hydrophathy.

5.5.2. *p*-Adic network in the genetic code

Networks play a very important role and there is a lot of interest in their investigation nowadays. Many systems can be considered as networks, which are the sets of nodes (vertices) joined together by links (edges). Examples can be found mainly within biological and social systems.

The genetic code also contains some aspects of the network that can be viewed as a *p*-adic network. Namely, 64 codons can be considered as a network in which the codons are nodes, and the 5-adic distances between them represent links. Recall that there are three possibilities of the 5-adic distance between codons: $\frac{1}{25}$, $\frac{1}{5}$ and 1. According to these distances, we can respectively call the corresponding subsets of codons as a small, intermediate and large network community. Thus, each codon has 3 neighbors at distance $\frac{1}{25}$ and makes a small world. Each codon is also linked to 12 and 48 other codons to make an intermediate and large community, respectively. Hence, any codon belongs simultaneously to a small, an intermediate and a large community.

Standard amino acids can also be seen as a *p*-adic network, where the amino acids are nodes and the 5-adic distances between them are links. It can be said that the genetic code links two *p*-adic networks to one larger

ultrametric network of 85 elements (64 codons + 20 amino acids + 1 stop signal). In these networks, the p -adic distances play the role of links.

5.5.3. Euclidean representation of p -adic genetic code

It is well known that common natural numbers can be represented as points on the real axis. Since p -adic numbers have different properties comparing to the real ones, they cannot be completely represented in the Euclidean space. However, by suitable mapping, the self-similar property of p -adic numbers can be represented in the Euclidean plane. This property is scale invariant, because of the power-law behavior of p -adic distance. In Fig. 2, we present 5-adic numbers,

$$x = x_0 + x_1 5 + x_2 5^2 \equiv x_0 x_1 x_2, \quad x_i \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}, \quad (36)$$

with relevant codons, as a fractal-like set in the Euclidean plane. For details on this representation, see our recent reference [20].

6. Concluding Remarks

In this paper, we have considered the genetic code modeling and pointed out the p -adic approach. We have shown that many properties of codons and amino acids, as well as the information flow from genes to proteins can be described using the p -adic distance. In the vertebrate mitochondrial code, two codons which are at the smallest 5-adic and 2-adic distance code the same amino acid or stop signal. Such two codons are the most similar in the sense of their genetic meaning.

The question now may be asked: How can this p -adic approach developed for codons be applied to the finite-length nucleotide sequences? For example, such a sequence may be microRNA (miRNA) (18-25 nucleotides) or tRNA (73-93 nucleotides). p -Adic distance can be used for these sequences and we plan to do so in our further research.

Mixing the p -adic distance with some other distances should also be interesting and useful. For example, one can modify the Hamming distance in the following way. Let $a = a_1 a_2 \cdots a_n$ and $b = b_1 b_2 \cdots b_n$ be two sequences of nucleotides of equal length. The Hamming distance between these two sequences is

$$d_H(a, b) = \sum_{i=1}^n d(a_i, b_i), \quad (37)$$

Figure 2. Euclidean representation of codons and amino acids of the vertebrate mitochondrial code (VMC) and the standard genetic code (SGC). Abbreviations within the base-digit assignment are related to the nucleobase type: Y - pyrimidine (C,U), R - purine (A,G); S - strong (C,G), W - weak (U,A); M - amino (C,A), K - keto (U,G), while N stands for any nucleobase. For the fourfold code degeneracy, it is always satisfied that the 5-adic distance between the amino acid and its cognate codons is $\frac{1}{25}$ (white positions), while for non-fourfold code degeneracy there are two values of the 5-adic distance: $\frac{1}{25}$ (light gray positions) and $\frac{1}{5}$ (dark gray positions). The two halves defined by the Y/R distinction of the first codon base have an equivalent arrangement of the fourfold and non-fourfold code degeneracy.

where $d(a_i, b_i) = 0$ if $a_i = b_i$, and $d(a_i, b_i) = 1$ if $a_i \neq b_i$. In other words, $d_H(a, b) = n - k$, where k is the number of positions at which the elements of both sequences are equal. One can introduce a 2-adic Hamming distance

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as

$$d_{2H}(a, b) = \sum_{i=1}^n d_2(a_i, b_i), \quad (38)$$

where $d_2(a_i, b_i) = |a_i - b_i|_2$ is 2-adic distance between nucleotides a_i and b_i . This 2-adic distance can be equal to 1 or $\frac{1}{2}$. The following inequality holds: $d_{2H}(a, b) \leq d_H(a, b)$.

On the similarity. In this article, we have used the notion of p -adic similarity. In general, the *similarity* of two objects a and b that belong to the metric space M , denoted by $\sigma(a, b)$, can be defined as

$$\sigma(a, b) = \frac{d_{max} - d(a, b)}{d_{max}}, \quad (39)$$

where d_{max} is maximum of distance at the space M . Thus the values of similarity can be: $0 \leq \sigma(a, b) \leq 1$. In the case of codons, the p -adic similarity between codons a and b is $\sigma_p = 1 - d_p(a, b)$, because $d_{max} = 1$. The similarity measured by the Hamming distance is $\sigma_H(a, b) = \frac{n - d_H(a, b)}{n}$, where n is the length of sequences a and b .

One can also introduce a Jaccard-like similarity between sequences a and b , whose lengths may be different, as follows. Let n and m be the length of sequences $a = a_1 a_2 \dots a_n$ and $b = b_1 b_2 \dots b_m$, respectively. Define the Jaccard-like distance as $d_J(a, b) = \frac{c}{n+m}$, where c is a number of different elements between these sequences. Then the Jaccard-like similarity is $\sigma_J(a, b) = \frac{n+m-c}{n+m}$. In this way $\sigma_J(a, b)$ measures the number of elements that are the same in sequences a and b , regardless of their position in the sequences. As an example, let sequence a contains 4 C, 2 A, 3 U, 1 G nucleotides and sequence b has 3 C, 2 A, 0 U, 2 G. Then $c = (4-3) + (2-2) + (3-0) + (2-1) = 5$ and the corresponding $\sigma_J(a, b) = \frac{17-5}{17} = \frac{12}{17}$.

In the case of similarity, the number of equal elements in two sequences should be taken into account:

- in p -adic similarity – counting from the beginning of the sequences to the first position where they differ,
- in Hamming similarity – counting in the same positions,
- in Jaccard-like similarity – counting regardless of positions.

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